

Studies on Some N-Acyl N-Phenylhydroxylamine as Metal Complexing Agents. Part XI. Extraction-Photometric Determination of Vanadium(V) with N-o-Tolyl N-hydroxysuccinamic Acid

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Vanadium (V) forms two coloured products with N-o-tolyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid ($R_1^oH_2$), a violet one with acid concentration of 1N or more and an orange one at pH values ≈ 2.5 to 5.5. In this report the extraction behaviour of the orange complex of V(V) with $R_1^oH_2$ has been investigated. *Iso*-amyl alcohol is used for the extraction which is quantitative within the pH range 4.23 to 4.93. A phosphate buffer (pH ≈ 4.6) has been employed for the purpose. Measurements are taken at the absorption maximum at 440 nm. For maximum intensity of the colour, which is stable for more than 12 hours, a 50-fold excess of the reagent in molar units, is required. Beer's law is obeyed from 1 to 10 ppm of V(V). Large excess of Na^+ , K^+ , Zn^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , UO_2^{2+} , Ti^{4+} , $Cr_2O_7^{2-}$, F^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , AC^- , SO_4^{2-} , phosphate and tartrate do not interfere. Fairly large amount of Fe^{3+} (5 moles per mole of V) can be tolerated probably due to presence of phosphate since in absence of phosphate there is interference. In presence of excess EDTA, V(V) is completely masked. The molar extinction co-efficient of the complex at 440 nm is 3725 ± 25 . Sensitivity (Sandell) is 0.013 γ of V per cm^2 .

SEVERAL organic reagents—cupferron¹, 8-hydroxyquinoline² have already been proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V). Recently a number of hydroxamic acids³⁻⁸ have been employed for the determination of V(V) in 2-8N HCl medium, by extraction photometry with chloroform. V(V) forms two coloured products with N-acyl-N-phenylhydroxylamines, a violet one with acid concentrations of 1N or more and an orange one at pH values ≈ 2.5 to 5.5. Recently N-m-nitrobenzoyl N-phenylhydroxylamine⁹ has been investigated for the extraction of the orange complex with *iso*-amyl alcohol which has been quantitative within the pH range 2.7 to 4.2. The extraction behaviour of the orange complex of V(V) with N-o-tolyl N-hydroxysuccinamic acid ($R_1^oH_2$)¹⁰ has been reported in this communication.

Experimental

Reagent : In the preparation of solutions double-distilled water was used. $R_1^oH_2$ was purified by recrystallization¹⁰. Other chemicals used were either of AR quality or properly purified. A 10% solution of KH_2PO_4 (pH ≈ 4.65 ; buffer solution) was chosen to maintain the desired pH during extraction. An aqueous solution of sodium vanadate was used which was standardised with Mohrsalt solution. Freshly prepared 0.4% ligand solution in *iso*-amyl alcohol was used.

Apparatus : Optical densities were measured with a spectrophotometer (UVISPEK) using 1 cm quartz cell. pH of the solutions were measured with a Cambridge pH-meter (portable type).

Procedure :

An aqueous solution containing 0.1 mg of V(V) was taken in a separatory funnel, pH of the solution was adjusted to 3-6 and 5 ml of buffer solution was added followed by water to make the volume 25-ml. Ligand solution [10 ml for each 100 γ of V(V)] was added and shaken vigorously. The layer was allowed to separate. The aqueous layer was collected in a beaker and the organic layer in a dry conical flask containing about 2g of anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The aqueous layer was washed twice with 5 ml portions of *iso*-amyl alcohol and the washings were collected in the same conical flask. Dried extract was transferred to a 25 ml measuring flask. The conical flask washed to remove the colour adhering to Na_2SO_4 . The washings were added to the main solution and diluted with *iso*-amyl alcohol upto mark. Optical densities were measured against solvent blank at wavelengths ranging from 360-600 nm. From the absorption curve the wavelength 440 nm (maximum) was selected for measurements.

Effect of pH or Acidity : In acidities above 1N in HCl a violet colour developed which faded away rapidly. The violet colour did not reappear on adding more ligand solution. V(V) was extracted from solutions having pH values from 2.6 to 5.9. The optimum pH range for quantitative extraction is 4.23 to 4.93. Results are stated below.

pH of solns. containing 100 γ of v	2.60	2.90	3.12	3.56	4.23	4.93	5.33	5.90
O.D.	0.227	0.282	0.290	0.292	0.298	0.298	0.288	0.276

Stability of the colour : The development of colour as well as extraction is very rapid. Vigorous shaking for 5 min is sufficient. The colour was found stable for 12 hr at room temperature (28°-35°).

Concentration of the reagent : For maximum intensity of colour, the reagent must be present at least 70 times excess in molar units. The optimum amount of the reagent is 8ml of 0.4% solution for each 100 γ of vanadium. Experimental data are shown below :

Volume in ml of 0.4% ligand solution added	2	4	8	10	12	14
O. D. of solns. containing 100 γ of vanadium.	0.268	0.290	0.298	0.298	0.298	0.298

Effect of number of extractions : The measurements of the absorbance of two successive extracts of an aqueous solution of V(V) with fresh ligand solution each time under optimal conditions showed that one such extraction was sufficient for quantitative transfer of V(V) into the *iso*-amyl alcohol layer.

Adherence to Beer's law : When the absorbance values were plotted against the concentrations, a straight line was obtained for 1-10 μ g of vanadium per 1 ml of *iso*-amyl alcohol.

Effect of diverse ions : Large excesses of Na⁺, K⁺, Zn²⁺, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, UO₂²⁺, Ti⁴⁺, Cr₂O₇²⁻, MoO₄²⁻, F⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻, NO₃⁻, Ac⁻, SO₄²⁻, phosphate, tartrate did not interfere. Fairly large amount of Fe³⁺ (5 moles per mole of V) could be tolerated probably due to presence of phosphate since in absence of phosphate there was interference. Small amount of Al³⁺ (2 moles per mole of V) did not interfere but large excess interfered. In presence of excess EDTA vanadium was completely masked.

Sensitivity : Molar extinction co-efficient of V(V) complex at 440 nm is 3725 \pm 25 and sensitivity according to Sandell's definition¹¹ is 0.0137 of V per cm². The optimal range of concentration of vanadium (absorbances ~0.2-0.7) is 3-10 μ g per ml of *iso*-amyl alcohol extract.

Accuracy and precision : The relative mean error and relative standard deviation are \pm 0.67% and \pm 0.35% respectively for the determination of

vanadium at its different concentrations. The results were obtained from a set of nine experiments under optimal conditions.

Discussion

The molar extinction co-efficient of the violet complexes of V(V) with the N-acyl N-phenylhydroxylamines are higher than those of the corresponding orange complexes. However, the violet complexes are more susceptible to reducing agents—traces of ethanol present in the chloroform hampers

the efficiency. Hence the method described here, though less sensitive, appears to be equally useful and probably safer. The molar extinction co-efficient of the orange V(V) complex with N-*m*-nitrobenzoyl N-phenylhydroxylamine has been found to be 3230 at 435 nm⁹, and that with the present ligand R₂^oH₂ is 3725 \pm 25 at 440 nm. So the method described here is more sensitive.

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